

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF A FAULT TOLERANT SCHEME FOR BRUSHLESS DC MOTOR DRIVE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a novel fault tolerant control system for Hall Effect position sensors failure of permanent magnet brushless DC (BLDC) motor in a closed loop control scheme. The proposed system is capable to detect and identify the Hall Effect sensors breakdown based on sensors signals and Fast Fourier Transform (DFT) analysis of the measured line voltages of motor. BLDC motor simulation model were validated first by experimental data under no fault condition. Analyzing the simulation results of the various sensor breakdowns leads to develop an expert system for Hall Effect sensors failure diagnosis in BLDC motor. A digital controller is presented to generate the commutation signal of faulty Hall Effect sensor to maintain the proper operation of BLDC motor after fault occurrence. The proposed fault tolerant control system does not need massive computational efforts and can be implemented as a subroutine in the main control program of the BLDC motor. The simulation results show correct performance of the proposed fault tolerant control system.

Key words: Fault tolerant control, Hall Effect sensor, Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

INTRODUCTION

The development and availability of very high-energy density brushless materials has contributed to an increased use of the brushless dc motor (BLDC) in high performance applications. High-speed electric machines are of interest as direct drives for high-speed milling machines, compressors and pumps, yielding a high output power at rather small machine dimensions. The high-speed BLDC (Brushless DC motor) is the best choice for high-speed operation because of the high efficiency, low torque ripple, low noise, and excellent control performance. The BLDC eliminates rotational cogging torque due to permanent magnet preferred positions, decreases core loss and thus increases efficiency, provides excellent torque-to volume and power-to volume ratios, and has a linear current versus torque relation. In the BLDC, in order to generate smooth torque and thus reduce noise and vibration, the current waveform should match the shape of the motor electromotive force (emf).

The objective of the project is to

analyze the hall sensor failure in bldc motor by FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) and SED (Spectral Energy Density) technique.

Failure of Hall Effect sensors effect directly on the applied voltages to the BLDC motor and degrade the performance of overall motor drive. Development of fault tolerant control systems increases reliability of electric motor drive. The fault tolerant control system mainly should accomplish the following tasks.

BRUSHLESS DC MOTOR

Brushless Direct Current (BLDC) motors are one of the motor types rapidly gaining popularity. BLDC motors are used in industries such as Appliances, Automotive, Aerospace, Consumer, Medical, Industrial, Automation, Equipment and Instrumentation. As the name implies BLDC motors do not use brushes for commutation instead they are electronically commutated.

BLDC motors have many advantages over brushed DC motors and induction motors.

A few of these are:

Better speed versus torque characteristics

- High dynamic response
- High efficiency
- Long operating life
- Noiseless operation
- Higher speed ranges

A brushless DC (BLDC) motor implements the basic operating principles of DC motor operation a bit differently by placing the permanent magnet in the rotor and coils in the stator. The coil windings are electrically separate from each other which allows them to be turned on and off in a sequence that creates a rotating magnetic field. In this case it's the field of the rotors permanent magnet ("chasing" the rotating stator field) that makes the rotor run.

It is necessary to know the rotor position so that excitation of the stator field always leads the permanent magnet field to produce torque. In a BLDC motor this function is provided by a commutation assembly consisting of electronic circuitry and a series of sensors (usually Hall Effect sensors). The circuitry decodes the sensor signals to determine the position of the shaft and energize the appropriate stator windings.

BLDC motors come in single-phase, 2-phase and 3-phase configurations. Corresponding to its type the stator has the same number of windings. Out of these 3-phase motors are the most popular and widely used.

BLDC motors are a type of synchronous motor. This means that the magnetic field generated by the stator and the magnetic field generated by the rotor rotate at the same frequency. BLDC motors do not experience the "slip" that is normally seen in induction motor

HALL SENSORS

The commutation of a BLDC motor is controlled electronically. To rotate the BLDC motor the stator windings should be energized in a sequence. It is important to know the rotor position in order to understand which winding will be energized following the energizing sequence. Rotor position is sensed using Hall Effect sensors embedded into the stator. By reading the Hall Effect sensors, a 3-bit code can be obtained with values ranging from 1 to 6. Each code value represents a sector on which the rotor is presently located. Each code value, therefore, gives us information on which windings need to be excited to turn the rotor. State '0' and '7' are invalid states for Hall Effect sensors.

The Hall sensors require a power supply. The voltage may range from 4 volts to 24 volts. The numbers in top of figure 2.4 correspond to the current phases. It is apparent that the three sensor outputs overlap in such a way as to create six unique three-bit codes corresponding to each of the drive phases. The numbers shown around the periphery of the motor represent the sensor position code.

Each drive phase consists of one motor terminal driven high and one motor terminal driven low and one motor terminal floating. The input sensor state and the corresponding drive state required for commutation

The switching sequence that should be followed with respect to the hall sensors. Every 60

electrical degrees of rotation one of the hall sensor changes state. It takes six steps to complete an electrical cycle. In synchronous with every 60 electrical degree the phase current switching should be updated. However, one electrical cycle may not correspond to a complete mechanical revolution of the rotor.

SENSOR VERSUS DRIVE TIMING

DYNAMICS OF A BLDC MOTOR

The dynamics of the machine are described by

a set of mathematical differential equations. To attain the electrical equations for a BLDC machine the basic circuit analysis was used to find the per-phase voltage as shown by equation 2.1. The equation is only shown for phase-a to neutral since the equations for phase b and c only differ in the subscript notation.

MODEL OF A BLDC MOTOR

BRUSHLESS DC (BLDC) DRIVE STRATEGIES

The operating characteristics of a BLDC motor are very similar to that of a brushed DC motor. Since a permanent magnet rotor is used in a BLDC the speed control can be implemented by varying the average voltage across the stator windings. This tends to change the value of the average stator current. However for a given load torque the average stator current has to be ideally fixed. Hence the back EMF induced in the stator windings has to change such that the stator current remains constant.

The three phase AC supply is converted into DC supply using power converter and the output stage consists of a three phase inverter composed of switches that could be MOSFETs or insulated-gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs). The BLDC control drive system is based on the feedback of rotor position using hall effectsensor and low cost digital control technique is proposed with a constant frequency digital PWM controller

BLDC MOTOR SYSTEM COMPONENTS

For a three phase BLDC application, the most common topology used is a three phase buck derived converter or a three phase inverter

bridge.

The output stage consists of a three-phase inverter composed of switches that could be MOSFETs or IGBTs. If IGBTs are used, antiparallel diodes need to be connected across them for carrying reverse currents, while MOSFETs use body diodes. MOSFETs give lower turn-off switching loss and usually lower diode forward drop, but that advantage may be offset by higher on-state voltage drop and turn-on switching/diode reverse recovery loss than IGBTs.

TYPICAL INVERTER DRIVE SYSTEM FOR A BLDC MOTOR

BRUSHLESS DC DRIVE STRATEGIES

One of the simplest methods of control for brushless dc motors using Trapezoidal commutation. In this scheme current is controlled through one pair motor terminals at a time and the third motor terminal always electrically disconnected from the source of power. Approximately the back EMF induced per phase of the motor winding is constant for 120° before and after which it changes linearly with rotor angle.

HALL EFFECT SENSOR

PHASE CURRENT WAVEFORM

Appropriate commutation therefore requires knowledge of rotor position which can be directly detected using position sensors or optical encoders. In any case, the phase current is essentially constant for the 120° conduction period. Hence the switch carries current for $1/3$ of one electrical rotation and the current is constant for a constant load. This can be used to calculate the switch conduction losses.

And PWM may be introduced during switch conduction giving rise to switching losses. Switching fashion depends upon the types of strategies employed. Controlling the speed amounts to changing the applied voltage across the motor phases. This can be done using sensed methods or sensor-less methods.

The Hall effect was discovered by Dr. Edwin Hall in 1879 while he was a doctoral candidate at Johns Hopkins University in Baltimore. Hall was attempting to verify the theory of electron flow proposed by Kelvin some 30 years earlier. Dr. Hall found when a magnet was placed so that its field was perpendicular to one face of a thin rectangle of gold through which current was flowing, a difference in potential appeared at the opposite edges. He found that this voltage was proportional to the current flowing through the conductor, and the flux density or magnetic induction perpendicular to the conductor.

The Hall element is the basic magnetic field sensor. It requires signal conditioning to make the output usable for most applications. The signal conditioning electronics needed are an amplifier stage and temperature compensation. Voltage regulation is needed when operating from an unregulated supply.

If the Hall voltage is measured when no magnetic field is present, the output is zero. However, if voltage at each output terminal is measured with respect to ground, a non-zero voltage will appear. This is the common mode voltage (CMV), and is the same at each output terminal. It is the potential difference that is zero. The amplifier shown in Figure must be a differential amplifier so as to amplify only the potential difference – the Hall voltage. The Hall voltage is a low-level signal on the order of 30 microvolts in the presence of a one gauss magnetic field. This low-level output requires an amplifier with low noise, high input impedance and moderate gain. A differential amplifier with these characteristics can be readily

integrated with the Hall element using standard bipolar transistor technology. Temperature compensation is also easily integrated equal, the Hall voltage is a function of the input current. The purpose of the regulator in Figure is to hold this current constant so that the output of the sensor only reflects the intensity of the magnetic field. As many systems have a regulated supply available, some Hall effect sensors may not include an internal regulator.

**SIMULINK
MATLABSIMULINK FOR GATE
SIGNAL LOGIC DESIGN**

MATLAB model of closed loop speed control of BLDC motor. This model contains three phase ac source, rectifier, universal bridge inverter, permanent magnet synchronous motor and controllers.

RESULTS

Case 1

Before fault the speed of brushless dc motor

Before fault the voltage waveform

Case 2

After fault the speed of brushless dc motor

After fault the voltage waveform

CONCLUSION

Fault tolerant control system for Hall Effect position sensors failure of BLDC motor is discussed. Behavior of BLDC motor is studied for position sensor failure situations. Fast Fourier transform analysis is used for pattern recognition of the line voltages and speed waveform of BLDC motor. Hall Effect sensor failure of BLDC motor is implemented on the verified simulation model. A knowledge based table is developed to identify the faulty sensor by analyzing the simulation results. Hence faulty position sensor is identified through spectral density error of the line voltages; exact knowledge of BLDC motor voltages for various speed and torque loads is not needed.

Commutation signal of faulty sensor is generated by microcontroller through correlation between Hall signals. The proposed fault tolerant system is capable to detect, identify and rectify the Hall Effect sensor break down in BLDC motor. Simulation results show correct detection and identification of position sensor fault by the proposed fault tolerant control system. Effectiveness of the remedial strategy is also proven by correct performance of BLDC motor under faulty condition

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